

IMPACT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ON BUSINESS OPERATIONS OF SMES IN ENUGU STATE

¹Enogwe, Grace Chisom, ²Prof. Fred O. Eze and ³Prof. Chris C. Orga

¹ESUT Business School, Department of Business Administration, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu State.

²Department of Public Administration, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu State.

³Department of Business Administration, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu State.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14680040>

Abstract: The study evaluated the impact of artificial intelligence on business operations of SMEs in Enugu State. The specific objectives were to: examine the impact of machine learning techniques on output and evaluate the impact of robotics on employee retention of SMEs in Enugu State. Descriptive survey design approach was adopted. A total population of 763 selected staff of the study firms. Sample size of two hundred and fifty-four (254) using Freund and William's statistic formula at 5 percent margin of error was adopted. Two hundred and forty-four (241) staff returned the questionnaire. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analyzed using Z – test statistic tool. The study revealed that Machine learning techniques had significant positive impact on output, $Z(95, n = 261), 5.323 < 9.842, P. <.05$ and Robotics had significant positive impact on employee retention of SMEs in Enugu State $Z(95, n = 261), 7.722 < 10.383, P. <.05$, The study concluded that Machine learning techniques and Robotics had significant positive impact on output and employee retention of SMEs in Enugu State. The study recommended among others the small and medium enterprises should endeavour to use Machine learning to help give enterprises a view of trends in customer behavior and operational business patterns, as well as supports the development of new products.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Business Operations, Machine Learning & Robotics.

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

Artificial intelligence in business operations is the use of machine learning models to help process business operations data and give business professionals important insights, improving business outcomes and customer experiences. The most common roles for AI in business operations settings are business decision support and imaging analysis. Business decision support tools help providers make decisions about treatments, medications, mental health and other patient needs by providing them with quick access to information or research that's relevant to their patient. In medical imaging, AI tools are being used to analyze CT scans, x-rays, MRIs and other images for lesions or other findings that a human radiologist might miss, (IBM, 2024).

Artificial intelligence (AI) with machine learning tools are used to search, store, and analyze medical data to benefit both physicians and the health of patients in various ways. With the advancement in machine learning

algorithms and bioinformatics techniques, AI has become an essential part of modern healthcare society. AI algorithms and deep learning applications support clinicians with managing health records, making diagnoses and clinical decisions, prescribing medication, determining mental health, and imaging analysis. Clinicians gain rapid access to information and research relevant to the needs of the patients. As some algorithms compete with and sometimes outperform clinicians, it is necessary to fully integrate this technology into daily medical practices, (Srivastava, 2024).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is becoming increasingly essential to the day-to-day operations of manufacturers all over the world. Autonomous robots and machine learning-powered predictive analytics means companies are able to streamline processes, increase productivity, Improve Efficiency and reduce the damage done to the environment in many new ways. Artificial intelligence can analyse data from important manufacturing process tools like sensors, machines, and people, then use programs to optimize operations and achieve efficient manufacturing.

However, the SMEs in Enugu state faces lack of machine learning, Natural language processing (NLP) Intelligent agents and robotics that aid in business operations. The drawbacks of AI include job displacement, ethical concerns about bias and privacy, security risks from hacking, and a lack of human-like creativity and empathy. Artificial Intelligence (AI) often lacks the intrinsic creativity of humans, which stems from emotional depth, abstract thinking, and imaginative processes. While AI can mimic creativity by generating art, music, or writing based on existing patterns, it doesn't possess genuine originality or the ability to think outside the box. The consequences of these if not tackled may lead to poor output, poor employee retention, sales etc. Based on this, the study aimed at evaluating the impact of artificial intelligence on business operations of SMEs in Enugu State.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to evaluate the impact of artificial intelligence on business operations of SMEs in Enugu State. The specific objectives were to:

- i. Examine the impact of machine learning techniques on output of SMEs in Enugu State.
- ii. Evaluate the impact of robotics on employee retention of SMEs in Enugu State.

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

- i. What is the impact of machine learning techniques on output of SMEs in Enugu State?
- ii. What is the impact of robotics on employee retention of SMEs in Enugu State?

1.5 Statement of Hypotheses

The following hypotheses guided the study

- i. Machine learning techniques have impact on output of SMEs in Enugu State.
- ii. Robotics has impact on employee retention of SMEs in Enugu State.

2.0 Review of Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Artificial Intelligence

Artificial intelligence is the simulation of human intelligence processes by machines, especially computer systems. Examples of AI applications include expert systems; natural language processing (NLP), speech recognition and machine vision (Craig, Laskowski & Tucci, 2024). AI is a field of research in computer science that develops and studies methods and software that enable machines to perceive their environment and use learning and intelligence to take actions that maximize their chances of achieving defined goals. Such machines may be called AIs. In general, AI systems work by ingesting large amounts of labeled training data, analyzing that data for correlations and patterns, and using these patterns to make predictions about future states. The terms AI, machine learning and deep learning are often used interchangeably, especially in companies' marketing materials, but they have distinct meanings. In short, AI describes the broad concept of machines simulating human intelligence, while machine learning and deep learning are specific techniques within this field. AI is an umbrella term that encompasses a wide variety of technologies, including machine learning, deep learning, and natural language processing (NLP). Although the term is commonly used to describe a range of different technologies in use today, many disagree on whether these actually constitute artificial intelligence. Instead, some argue that much of the technology used in the real world today actually constitutes highly advanced machine learning that is simply a first step towards true artificial intelligence, or “general artificial intelligence” (GAI) (Coursera, 2024). The synergies between artificial intelligence (AI) technologies and manufacturing are well known. Among the earliest adopters of computer-based tech in the 1970s, the manufacturing industry has grown into an AI-heavyweight in the 21st century (Singh, 2024).

2.1.2 Components of Artificial intelligence

2.1.2.1 Machine Learning Techniques

Machine learning is now one of the main drivers of manufacturing digital transformation, poised to transform the majority of labor- and data-intensive manufacturing processes and improve companies' operational efficiency. In the manufacturing context, machine learning algorithms are applied to process large volumes of data about the production, equipment, and products to help optimize time-consuming aspects of the manufacturing process, including quality control, equipment maintenance, and product design. Implementing machine learning- and Internet of Thing-enabled systems, manufacturing organizations can monitor equipment conditions and take proactive repair measures. Installed sensors retrieve data from machinery components and send it to an ML-based analytics system, which automatically detects performance deviations and predicts equipment's remaining useful life and when it's going to fail (Itransition, 2024). Machine learning models are also being used for product inspection and quality control. Machine learning enables predictive maintenance by predicting production line equipment failures before they occur, scheduling timely maintenance, and reducing unnecessary production downtime. ML-based computer vision algorithms can learn from historical data to distinguish good products from faulty ones, automating the inspection and supervision process. Machine learning offers significant savings in visual quality control in manufacturing (IT Convergence, 2020).

2.1.2.2 Robotics

The term robotics is an extension of the word robot. One of its first uses came from Czech writer Karel Čapek, who used the word in his 1920 play, *R.U.R.* Robotics is an interdisciplinary sector of science and engineering dedicated to the design, construction and use of mechanical robots. Robotics is the intersection of science, engineering and technology that produces machines, called robots, that replicate or substitute for human actions. Robots

perform basic and repetitive tasks with greater efficiency and accuracy than humans, making them ideal for industries like manufacturing. However, the introduction of artificial intelligence in robotics has given robots the ability to handle increasingly complex situations in various industries (Daley, 2024). The goal of most robotics is to design machines that can help and assist humans. Many robots are built to do jobs that are hazardous to people, such as finding survivors in unstable ruins, and exploring space, mines and shipwrecks. Others replace people in jobs that are boring, repetitive, or unpleasant, such as cleaning, monitoring, transporting, and assembling. Today, robotics is a rapidly growing field, as technological advances continue; researching, designing, and building new robots serve various practical purposes.

2.1.3 Business Operations

Business operations are the collection of routine tasks and processes a business performs to generate revenue. Efficient operations make the most of a company's resources, reducing costs associated with day-to-day activities and increasing the company's output. Business operations refer to activities that businesses engage in on a daily basis to increase the value of the enterprise and earn a profit. The activities can be optimized to generate sufficient revenues to cover expenses and earn a profit for the owners of the business. Employees help accomplish the business' goals by performing certain functions such as marketing, accounting, manufacturing, etc. (CFL Teams, 2024). Essentially, biz ops are about strategically managing a company's resources, making its processes standardized, smoothed and streamlined. That way, costs can go down, employee performance can go up and the organization can run more efficiently (Urvin, 2024).

2.1.4 Components of Business Operations used

2.1.4.1 Output

Output is the quantity of goods or services produced in a given time period, by a firm, industry, or country whether consumed or used for further production. Output is the result of an economic process that has used inputs to produce a product or service that is available for sale or use somewhere else (Wikipedia, 2013). Output is the measure of production against efficiency. It crops up a lot in everyday conversation (Down, 2019). Output refers to the total production of goods and services of a whole country over a given period – its gross domestic product. The term may refer to all the work, energy, goods, or services produced by an individual, company, factory or machine (Market Business News, 2022).

2.1.4.2 Employee retention

Employee retention refers to an organization's ability to retain quality employees. The retention rate is often expressed as a percentage and the goal is for it to be high, (Herrity, 2023). Employee retention is a phenomenon where employees choose to stay on with their current company and don't actively seek other job prospects. Employee retention is defined as an organization's ability to prevent employee turnover, or the number of people who leave their job in a certain period, either voluntarily or involuntarily. Increasing employee retention has a direct impact on business performance and success. The opposite of retention is turnover, where employees leave the company for a variety of reasons, (BasuMallick, 2021)

2.1.5 Conceptual Framework

Source: Researcher, 2024

2.2 Theoretical Framework

The following theories guided the study:

The study was theoretical underpinned on Technology acceptance model by Fred Davis in 1989. The study was anchored on Technology acceptance model (TAM) because it assumes that individuals' perceptions of a technology's usefulness and ease of use are influenced by various factors such as their prior experiences, social influences, and perceived compatibility with existing practices.

2.2.1 Technology Acceptance Model

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), developed by Fred Davis in 1989, TAM offers valuable insights into how artificial intelligence (AI) adoption and utilization of business operation measures may affect their overall performance. One of the fundamental assumptions of TAM is that individuals are rational actors who assess the potential benefits and costs associated with adopting a new technology (Davis, 1989). They are inclined to adopt technologies that they perceive as advantageous and user-friendly. Additionally, TAM assumes that individuals' perceptions of a technology's usefulness and ease of use are influenced by various factors such as their prior experiences, social influences, and perceived compatibility with existing practices (Davis, 1989). Therefore, in the context of the study, SME owners and employees' perceptions of artificial intelligence tools and practices are likely to be influenced by their past experiences with similar technologies, feedback from peers or industry experts, and how seamlessly these tools integrate into their existing business processes.

2.3 Empirical Review

2.3.1 The impact of machine learning techniques on output of SMEs in Enugu State.

Thu, Beppu, Yarime and Shibayama (2022) did a study on Role of Machine Learning and Organizational Structure in Science. The progress of science increasingly relies on machine learning (ML) and machines work alongside humans in various domains of science. This study investigates the team structure of ML-related projects and analyzes the contribution of ML to scientific knowledge production under different team structure, drawing on bibliometric analyses of 25,000 scientific publications in various disciplines. Our regression analyses suggest that (1) interdisciplinary collaboration between domain scientists and computer scientists as well as the engagement of interdisciplinary individuals who have expertise in both domain and computer sciences are common in ML-related projects; (2) the engagement of interdisciplinary individuals seem more important in achieving high impact and novel discoveries, especially when a project employs computational and domain approaches interdependently; and (3) the contribution of ML and its implication to team structure depend on the depth of ML.

Nayem and Uddin (2024) carried out research on Unbiased Employee Performance Evaluation Using Machine Learning. Most of the companies' sustainability and growth depend on how well its employees perform. However, the measurement of employees' performance until now is inconclusive and in exhaustive. To accurately assess and predict an employee's performance, numerous external factors (physical/environmental, social, and economic) related to an employee's life have been taken into account in this work. The purpose of

this research is to explore an unbiased AI algorithmic solution to predict future employee performance considering physical, social, and economic environmental factors that affect employee performance. We collected data of 1109 employees from the 'For-Profit Organization' in Bangladesh from both employers and employees to cover all the factors that justified the unbiased outcome. We utilized a few machine learning tools in this study including the Logistic Regression classifier, the Gaussian Naive Bayes, the Decision Tree classifier, the K-Nearest Neighbors (K-NN), the SVM classification, etc., in order to predict the employee performance evaluation. Then, we compared the effectiveness of those machine learning models by analyzing their precisions, recall, F1-score, and accuracy.

Nahar, Akhter and Sharturaev (2024) researched on the Impact of Artificial Intelligence on the Human Resources Management. This research article aims to explore and assess the influence of music education on cognitive development in children. Drawing upon various theories and previous studies, the research seeks to provide a comprehensive analysis of the potential benefits of music education in enhancing cognitive abilities such as memory, attention, problem-solving, and language skills. A thorough literature review was conducted, encompassing studies from diverse disciplines, including psychology, education, neuroscience, and music therapy. The review revealed that exposure to music activates multiple regions of the brain involved in cognitive processes, suggesting a strong interconnection between music and cognitive development. The findings indicated that music education, with its structured learning, practice, and performance elements, could actively contribute to the cognitive growth of children.

Zhang, Antwi-Afari, Zhang and Xing (2024) examined the Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Organizational Justice and Project Performance: A Systematic Literature and Science Mapping Review. By adopting a systematic literature and science mapping review, this paper aims to explore the impact of artificial intelligence (AI) on organizational justice and project performance. A total of 47 bibliographic records from the Scopus database were analyzed. The results revealed the annual publication trends of research articles and relevant peer-reviewed journals in the studied domain. It was found that while AI technology has made significant progress in several fields, its application areas in project management and organizational justice are still relatively low. Moreover, it objectively discussed the co-occurrence analysis of keywords, co-authors, countries/regions, and documents in the fields, revealing the current research topics. The main research topics include the (1) AI's influence on organizational justice, decision analysis, and digital transformation, (2) fostering organizational justice and AI's role in enhancing project performance, and (3) improving organizational performance approaches. Furthermore, this paper proposed research gaps and future research directions, including (1) advancing business intelligence strategies, (2) unlocking AI technology potential on organizational justice and project performance, (3) the adaptation of cultural, diversity, environmental, and social factors, (4) the impact of AI on complex and challenging leadership styles, and (5) developing a comprehensive understanding of the agile framework. The findings of this paper could contribute to a better understanding of how AI shapes project/construction management and organizational justice, providing practical solutions for innovative development for researchers and policymakers.

2.3.2 The impact of robotics on employee retention of SMEs in Enugu State.

Oshogbunu, Amah and Okocha (2022) investigated Management by Objective and Organizational Productivity: A Literature Review. The main aim of this study is to examine Management by Objectives as an instrument for improving organizational productivity. Management by objectives is a prominent management technique that cuts across or pervades all human activities, including business, education, government, health care, and non-profit organizations. It is not merely a managerial strategy for achieving well-coordinated managerial goals. Unfortunately, many firms have yet to use this strategy for gaining employee engagement and support. Subsequently, the objective of this research is to look into the connection between objective management and organizational production. More specifically, this paper intends to understand and describe the idea of management by objective (participation, goal setting and performance appraisal) and how it affects organizational productivity vis-à-vis market share and profitability. This study was conducted using the qualitative approach framework which include the review of related literature in regards to the topic using journals, textbooks and other related document. From the discussion of findings, it was concluded that for any organizations to be productive and achieve sustained success, it must continuously encourage management by objective since it is very essential in attaining and sustaining organizational productivity. We recommended among others that managers should involve employees in setting and identifying short and long-term departmental goals.

Isiaka, Jimoh, Orebiyi & Adenekan (2022) conducted a study on the effect of cost control strategies on the survival of manufacturing sector in Nigeria, using panel data gathered from annual reports of five selected firms for the period five (5) years between 2015 and 2019. Data on finance cost, salaries, and wages, and sales cost were taken as independent variables to measure the level at which manufacturing companies have been able to manage their costs while return on asset (Income/Total Asset) was taken as dependent variable proxied the performance of manufacturing companies. The study revealed that finance cost and cost of goods sold were insignificant cost to influence the performance of manufacturing sector, however, salaries and wages pose a significant impact on financial performance of manufacturing sector in Nigeria.

Suleiman, Mustapha and Agbi (2023) conducted a study on how cost management and reduction affect Nigerian manufacturing companies' profitability. The 78 manufacturing companies registered on the Nigerian Stock Exchange make up the study's population, and a sample of one of these companies was used for the study throughout a ten-year period (2012–2021). Data for the project was gathered from the chosen company's audited financial filings. Multiple regressions were used to assess the data that had been collected. The analysis's findings showed that administrative costs have a big impact on profitability. However, Nestle Nig. Plc's profitability is adversely and negligibly impacted by both finance expenses and fluctuations in the cost of materials. The study came to the conclusion that Nestle Nigeria Plc's profitability is significantly impacted by cost control and cost reduction.

Mikalef, Islam, Parida, Singh and Altwaijry (2023) did research on Artificial intelligence (AI) competencies for organizational performance: A B2B marketing capabilities perspective. The deployment of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has been accelerating in several fields over the past few years, with much focus placed on its potential in Business-to-Business (B2B) marketing. Early reports highlight promising benefits of AI in B2B marketing such as offering important insights into customer behaviors, identifying critical market insight, and

streamlining operational inefficiencies. Nevertheless, there is a lack of understanding concerning how organizations should structure their AI competencies for B2B marketing, and how these ultimately influence organizational performance. Drawing on AI competencies and B2B marketing literature, this study develops a conceptual research model that explores the effect that AI competencies have on B2B marketing capabilities, and in turn on organizational performance. The proposed research model is tested using 155 survey responses from European companies and analyzed using partial least squares structural equation modeling. The results highlight the mechanisms through which AI competencies influence B2B marketing capabilities, as well as how the later impact organizational performance.

2.4 Summary of Empirical Review Literature

The studies done were carried outside impact of artificial intelligence on business operations of SMEs in Enugu State and did not focus to best of my knowledge on the machine learning techniques on productivity, robotics on customer service of SMEs in Enugu State. Most of the studies reviewed analysed their data through A purposeful sampling technique, Descriptive statistics and appropriate inferential statistics, Purposive Sampling technique, Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient, Multiple sampling technique, Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA) method, Simple linear regression and Pearson correlation coefficient (r) while the present study made use of Z test to test the hypotheses. Therefore, the study aimed at filling this research gap by evaluating the impact of artificial intelligence on business operations of SMEs in Enugu State.

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The study employed descriptive survey design. The survey research is one in which a group of people or items is studied by collecting and analyzing data from only a few people or items considered to be representative of the entire group. The survey design was adopted because the study required a technique of observation such as questionnaire and or interview, the population of the study must be carefully chosen, clearly defined and specifically delimited and roles upon observation for the acquisition of data.

3.2 Source of Data

Data are classified as either primary or secondary data. The classification was based on the two possible sources: primary source and secondary source.

3.2.1 Primary Source

The primary source was questionnaire. A primary data source is the one which the data is collected directly (usually first-hand) by the researcher.

3.2.2 Sources of Secondary Data

Secondary data source is the one which the data is obtained from published materials, internet websites, reports, dailies, text books and so on from the library of the institutions understudy. Sources of secondary can be split into two parts internal and external sources.

3.3 Area of Study

The area of the study was Enugu State, Nigeria. The areas include: Coco Cola and 7up comp, 9th Mile, Innoson Company, Emene, JUHEL industries, Emene and Shoprite Polo.

3.4 Population of the Study

The population of the study were five (5) selected organizations in Enugu state. The population of the study was seven hundred and fifty-three (753) which consists of selected employees both male and female of different carders in the selected organizations that believed to have effective knowledge of the organizations.

Table 3.1: Breakdown of the population size

Organisations	Number	%
Coco Cola	132	18%
7up comp	114	15%
Innoson com.	143	19%
JUHEL Indus.	244	32%
Shoprite Polo	120	16%
Total	753	100%

Source: Field survey, 2024.

3.5 Determination of Sample Size

To determine the adequate sample size, the study used Freund and William's statistic formula as quoted by (Uzoagulu 2011). Table 3.1 for details.

$$n = \frac{Z^2 N(pq)}{N(e)^2 + Z^2(pq)}$$

Where n = Sample Size

N = The population

p = Probability of success/proportion

q = Probability of failure/proportion

Z = Standard error of the mean

e = Limit of tolerable error of 0.05 (or level of significance)

N = 753

p = .5

q = (1 - .5) = .5

Z = 95 percent = 1.96

e = 0.05 percent

$$= \frac{(1.96)^2 \times 753 \times .5 \times .5}{753(0.05)^2 + (1.96)^2 \times .5 \times .5}$$

$$= \frac{3.8416 \times 753 \times .25}{1.8825 + 3.8416 \times .25}$$

$$\frac{723.181}{1.885 + .9604} = \frac{723.181}{2.8454} = 254.157 \quad \underline{\underline{\sim 254}}$$

3.6 Sample Size Determination

Bowley's (1937) proportional allocation statistic was utilized to ensure equitable representation of the organisations. Bowley's (1937) Formula:

$$N_h = \frac{n \times N_h}{N}$$

Where nh = number of questionnaires allocated to each of the institution

- n = Total sample size
- N_h = Number of proposed lecturers to be used from the selected organizations
- N = Population size.

Table 3.2: Questionnaire Allocation to each organisations

Name of the organisations	Population	Calculation	Sample
1. Coco Cola	132	$\frac{132 \times 254}{753}$	45
2. 7up comp	114	$\frac{114 \times 254}{753}$	39
3. Innoson com.	143	$\frac{143 \times 254}{753}$	48
4. JUHEL Indus.	244	$\frac{244 \times 254}{753}$	82
5. Shoprite Polo	120	$\frac{120 \times 254}{753}$	40
Total	753		254

Source: Author’s field work 2024

3.7 Sampling Technique

The stratified random sampling with a random start was adopted so as to give every unit of the population under study equal opportunity of being selected into sample. The secondary data were collected from firms, journals, publication, textbooks and the internet. Ten questions (10) in the questionnaire were ranged.

3.8 Instrument for Data Collection

The main instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire. Copies of the questionnaire were administered to the academic staff. Ten (10) designed questionnaire was used. The responses generated were used thereafter for data analyses.

3.9 Validity of the Instrument

The instrument was given to two experts from the industry and academia to measure face and content validity. To make sure that the research instruments applied in the work are valid, the research ensured that the instrument measure the concept they are supposed to measure.

3.10 Reliability of the Research Instrument

This was done by administering 20 copies of the prepared questionnaire to the sample of the study. Cronbah’s Alpha was used in determining the extent of consistency of the reliability. A Cronbach’s alpha value (∞) of greater 0.820 indicated very strong reliability.

Scale: ALL VARIABLES

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	10	100.0
	Excluded	0	.0
	Total	10	100.0

- a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	No. of Items
.82	10

Scale reliability was calculated using Cronbach's Alpha; the result obtained was 0.820. This shows that the internal consistency of the scale is good for the purpose of this study because it is greater than 0.82 which was good.

3.11 Method of Data Analyses

Data from the questionnaire were analyzed with the aid of SPSS version 23 using simple, percentages and correlation co-efficient. Data from the questionnaire were further analyzed using simple percentages, mean and standard deviation. For the 5-point likert scale questions, the scale and decision rule stated below were used in analysing the findings.

Scale: Strongly Agree (SA) = 5, Agree (A) = 4, Neutral (N) = 3, Disagree (D) = 2, Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1.

Decision Rule: If Mean > 3.0, the respondents agree and If mean ≤3.0, the respondents disagree. The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r otherwise rejects the null hypothesis and Z - test was used to test the hypotheses and analyzed with the aid of SPS

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

4.1 Distribution and returned Questionnaire

The chapter presents and analyzes the data collected for the study. The presentation and interpretation of data were based on the questionnaire administrated to the staff of the organisations under study. Table 4.1 shows the Distribution and Return of the Questionnaire from the organisations. Two hundred and fifty-four (254) copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the respondents and two hundred and forty-one (241) copies were returned representing Ninety-five (95) percent, while thirteen (13) copies of the questionnaire were not returned representing five (5) percent. That showed a high rate of response.

4.2 Data Presentation

4.2.1 Impact of machine learning techniques on output of SMEs in Enugu State.

Table 4.2.1.1: Responses on the impact of machine learning techniques on productivity of SMEs in Enugu State.

		5 SA	4 A	3 N	2 DA	1 SD	∑FX X	- SD	Decision
1	Machine learning is being able to leverage that experience for new opportunities that promote growth	430 86 33.0	92 23 8.8	255 85 32.6	84 42 16.1	25 25 9.6	886 241 100.0	3.67 1.342	Agree
2	The machine learning offers automation of repetitive tasks that enhances output in the organization	670 134 51.3	92 23 8.8	114 38 14.6	80 40 15.3	26 26 10.0	982 241 100.0	4.07 1.456	Agree
3	The large volume of data is efficiency handled with machine learning which decreases operational costs	515 103 39.5	92 23 8.8	213 71 27.2	60 30 11.5	34 34 13.0	914 241 100.0	3.79 1.435	Agree
4	Faster and surer of decision making are relied on machine learning that optimizing resources	575 115 44.1	232 58 22.2	96 32 12.3	56 28 10.7	28 28 10.7	987 241 100.0	4.10 1.385	Agree
5	Accuracy, precision and fraud detection	795	160	63	42	20	1080	4.48 1.299	Agree

are more quickly done by using machine learning.	159 60.9	40 15.3	21 8.0	21 8.0	20 7.7	241 100.0
--	-------------	------------	-----------	-----------	-----------	--------------

Total Grand mean and standard deviation						20.11	6.917
---	--	--	--	--	--	-------	-------

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 4.2.1.1, 109 respondents out of 241 representing 41.8 percent agreed that Machine learning is being able to leverage that experience for new opportunities that promotes growth with mean score 3.67 and standard deviation of 1.342. 157 respondents representing 60.1 percent agreed that The machine learning offers automation of repetitive tasks that enhances output in the organization with mean score of 4.07 and standard deviation of 1.456. 126 respondents representing 48.3 percent agreed that the large volume of data are efficiency handled with machine learning which decreases operational costs with mean score of 3.79 and standard deviation of 1.435 173 respondents representing 66.3 percent agreed that Faster and more sure of decision making are relied on machine learning that optimizing resources with mean score of 4.10 and 1.385. 199 respondents representing 76.2 percent agreed that Accuracy, precision and fraud detection are more quickly done by using machine learning. With a mean score of 4.48 and standard deviation 1.299

4.2.2. Impact of robotics on employee retention of SMEs in Enugu State

Table 4.2.2.1: Responses on the impact of robotics on customer service of SMEs in Enugu State

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		
1	Robots help achieve faster customers services and promotes competitive advantage	605	276	27	78	23	1009	4.19	1.370	Agree
		121	69	9	39	23	241			
		46.4	26.4	3.4	14.9	8.8	100.0			
2	More efficient production lines with robots held reduce capital costs associated with inventory	645	308	36	24	31	1044	4.33	1.342	Agree
		129	77	12	12	31	241			
		49.4	29.5	4.6	4.6	11.9	100.0			
3	Robots produces more accurate and high-quality work and enhances customer reputation	795	296	27	12	13	1143	4.74	1.022	Agree
		159	74	9	6	13	241			
		60.9	28.4	3.4	2.3	5.0	100.0			
4	The use of robots help produces a greater quality in a short amount of time to service customer needs	715	344	27	24	11	1121	4.65	1.031	Agree
		143	86	9	12	11	241			
		54.8	33.0	3.4	4.6	4.2	100.0			
5	Robots rarely make mistakes and are more precise that promotes customers loyalty.	470	368	27	90	21	976	4.05	1.322	Agree
		94	92	9	45	21	241			
		36.0	35.2	3.4	17.2	8.0	100.0			
Total Grand mean and standard deviation							21.96	6.087		

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 4.2.2.1, 190 respondents out of 241 representing 72.8 percent agreed that Robots help achieve faster customers services and promotes competitive advantage with mean score 4.19 and standard deviation of 1.370.206 respondents representing 51.9 percent agreed that more efficient production lines with robots held reduce capital costs associated with inventory with mean score of 4.33 and standard deviation of 1.342. 233 respondents representing 89.3 percent agreed that Robots produces more accurate and high-quality work and enhances customer reputation with mean score of 4.74 and standard deviation of 1.022. 229 respondents representing 87.8 percent agreed that the use of robots help

produces a greater quality in a short amount of time to service customer needs with mean score of 4.65 and standard deviation of 1.031. 186 respondents representing 71.2 percent agreed that Robots rarely make mistakes and are more precise that promotes customers loyalty with a mean score of 4.05 and standard deviation 1.132.

4.3 Test of Hypotheses

4.3.1 Hypothesis One: Machine learning techniques has impact on output of SMEs in Enugu State

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Machine learning is being able to leverage that experience for new opportunities that promotes growth	The machine learning offers automation of repetitive tasks that enhances output in the organization	The large volume of data is efficiency handled with machine learning which decreases operational costs	Faster and surer of decision making are relied on machine learning that optimizing resources	Accuracy, precision and fraud detection are more quickly done by using machine learning.
N		261	261	261	261	261
Uniform Parameters ^{a,b}	Minimum	1	1	1	1	1
	Maximum	5	5	5	5	5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute Positive	.330	.513	.395	.441	.609
	Positive	.096	.100	.130	.107	.077
	Negative	-.330	-.513	-.395	-.441	-.609
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		5.323	8.294	6.376	7.118	9.842
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

a. Test distribution is Uniform.

b. Calculated from data.

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value of 5.323 <9.842 and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms the assertion of the most of the respondents that Machine learning techniques had significant positive impact on output of SMEs in Enugu State

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value of 5.323 <9.842 against the critical Z- value of .000 (2-tailed test at 97 percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis was rejected. Thus, the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that Machine learning techniques had significant positive impact on output of SMEs in Enugu State

4.3.2 Hypothesis Two: Robotics has impact on employee retention of SMEs in Enugu State.

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Robots help achieve faster customers services and promotes competitive advantage	More efficient production lines with robots held reduce capital costs associated with inventory	robots produces more accurate and high quality work and enhances customer reputation	The use of robots help produces a greater quality in a short amount of time to service customer needs	robots rarely make mistakes and are more precise that promotes customers loyalty.
N		261	261	261	261	261
Uniform Parameters ^{a,b}	Minimum	1	1	1	1	1
	Maximum	5	5	5	5	5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute Positive	.478	.539	.643	.627	.463
	Positive	.088	.119	.050	.042	.080
	Negative	-.478	-.539	-.643	-.627	-.463

Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z	7.722	8.712	10.383	10.136	7.474
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

a. Test distribution is Uniform.

b. Calculated from data.

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value of $7.722 < 10.383$ and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms the assertion of the most of the respondents that **Robotics had significant positive impact on employee retention of SMEs in Enugu State.**

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value of $7.722 < 10.383$ against the critical Z- value of .000 (2-tailed test at 97percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis were rejected. Thus the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that **Robotics had significant positive impact on employee retention of SMEs in Enugu State.**

4.4 Discussion of findings

4.4.1 Machine learning techniques has impact on output of SMEs in Enugu State.

From the result of hypothesis one, the calculated Z- value of $5.323 < 9.842$ against the critical Z- value of .000, which implies that Machine learning techniques had significant positive impact on output of SMEs in Enugu State. In support of the result in the literature, Nayem and Uddin, (2024) Unbiased Employee Performance Evaluation Using Machine Learning. Most of the companies’ sustainability and growth depend on how well its employees perform. Then, we compared the effectiveness of those machine learning models by analyzing their precisions, recall, F1-score, and accuracy. This work can be utilized to obtain bias-free employee performance reviews. This fair employee performance assessment can aid decision-makers in making moral choices regarding employee promotions, career advance-ment, and training needs, among other things. Nahar, Akhter and Sharturaev, (2024) Impact of Artificial Intelligence on the Human Resources Management. The findings indicated that music education, with its structured learning, practice, and performance elements, could actively contribute to the cognitive growth of children. This research article concludes by discussing the implications of these findings for educators, policymakers, and parents.

4.4.2 Robotics has impact on employee retention of SMEs in Enugu State.

From the result of hypothesis one, the calculated Z- value of $7.722 < 10.383$ against the critical Z- value of .000 which implies that Robotics had significant positive impact on employee retention of SMEs in Enugu State. In support of the result in the literature, De Backer, and DeStefano, (2021). Robotics and the Global Organisation of Production. In: von Braun, Archer, Reichberg, Sánchez Sorondo, (eds) Robotics, AI, and Humanity. The effects of robots on economies go further than employment effects, as there are impacts for the organisation of production in global value chains. These change the division of labour between richer and poorer economies. Robotics may reduce off shoring of activities from developed economies towards emerging economies. Global spreading of automation with robotics can lead to faster de-industrialisation in the development process. Low-

cost jobs in manufacturing may increasingly be conducted by robots such that fewer jobs than expected may be on offer for humans even if industries were to grow in emerging economies. Oshogbunu, Amah and Okocha, (2022) Management by Objective and Organizational Productivity: A Literature Review. From the discussion of findings, it was concluded that for any organizations to be productive and achieve sustained success, it must continuously encourage management by objective since it is very essential in attaining and sustaining organizational productivity. We recommended among others that managers should involve employees in setting and identifying short and long-term departmental goals.

5.0 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of Findings

- i. Machine learning techniques had significant positive impact on output of SMEs in Enugu State, $Z(95, n = 261), 5.323 < 9.842, p < .05$
- ii. Robotics had significant positive impact on employee retention of SMEs in Enugu State $Z(95, n = 261), 7.722 < 10.383, p < .05$

5.2 Conclusion

The study concluded that Machine learning techniques and Robotics had significant positive impact on output and employee retention of SMEs in Enugu State. Artificial intelligence analytics allow business owners to better understand customer needs, streamline processes, reduce risks and spot fraud more easily, predict demand more accurately, and make informed business decisions more efficiently. It can be used to identify tasks and processes ideal for automation and assist with automating workflows. Applications of Artificial intelligence for business development automation include managing accounts, identifying upsell and cross-sell opportunities, and improving retention rates.

5.3 Recommendations

- i. The Small and medium enterprises should endeavour to use Machine learning to help give enterprises a view of trends in customer behavior and operational business patterns, as well as supports the development of new products.
- ii. The management of SMEs should practice the use of Robots to eliminate dangerous jobs for humans because they are capable of working in hazardous environments. They can handle lifting heavy loads, toxic substances and repetitive tasks.

5.4 Contribution to Knowledge

The studies done were carried outside impact of artificial intelligence on business operations of SMEs in Enugu State and did not focus to best of my knowledge on the machine learning techniques on output, robotics on employee retention of SMEs in Enugu State. Most of the studies reviewed analysed their data through. A purposeful sampling technique, Descriptive statistics and appropriate inferential statistics, Purposive Sampling technique, Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient, Multiple sampling technique, Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA) method, Simple linear regression and Pearson correlation coefficient (r) while the present study made use of Z test to test the hypotheses. Therefore, the study aimed at filling this research gap by evaluating the impact of artificial intelligence on business operations of SMEs in Enugu State.

References

BasuMallick, C. (2021). What is retention? <https://www.spiceworks.com/hr/engagement-retention/articles/what-is-employee-retention/>

Biesok, G., & Wrobel, J. W. (2011). Customer satisfaction: Meaning and methods of measuring. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/318013354_Customer_satisfaction_-_Meaning_and_methods_of_measuring

CFI Teams. (2024). What are business operations?

Coursera, S. (2024). What is artificial intelligence? Definition, uses, and types. <https://www.coursera.org/articles/what-is-artificial-intelligence>

Craig, L., Laskowski, N., & Tucci, L. (2024). What is artificial intelligence (AI)? Everything you need to know. <https://www.techtarget.com/searchenterpraiseai/definition/AI-Artificial-Intelligence>

Daley, S. (2024). Robotics technology. <https://builtin.com/robotics>

De Backer, K., & DeStefano, T. (2021). Robotics and the global organisation of production. In J. von Braun, S. Archer, M. Reichberg, & G. M. Sánchez Sorondo (Eds.), *Robotics, AI, and humanity*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-54173-6_6

Down, T. (2019). How to measure employee productivity. <https://www.breathehr.com/en-gb/blog/topic/employee-performance/how-to-measure-employee-productivity>

Herrity, J. (2023). Employee retention. <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/definition-of-employee-retention>

IBM. (2024). What is artificial intelligence (AI)? <https://www.ibm.com/topics/artificial-intelligence>

Isiaka, N. A., Jimoh, A. A., Orebiyi, M. A., & Adenekan, S. A. (2022). The effect of cost control on the survival of manufacturing sectors in Nigeria: Panel data analysis. *Asean International Journal of Business*, 1(2), 61–73. <https://doi.org/10.54099/aijb.v1i2.176>

IT Convergence. (2020). 6 benefits of machine learning in manufacturing. <https://www.itconvergence.com/blog/6-benefits-of-machine-learning-in-manufacturing/>

ITransition, C. (2024). Machine learning in manufacturing: Key applications, examples & adoption guidelines. <https://www.itransition.com/machine-learning/manufacturing>

Jill, H. (2019). The importance of employee productivity. <https://bizfluent.com/info-8292773-importance-employee-productivity.html>

- Market Business News. (2022). What is output? Definition and meaning. <https://marketbusinessnews.com/financial-glossary/output-definition-meaning/>
- Mikalef, P., Islam, N., Parida, V., Singh, & Altwaijry, N. (2023). Artificial intelligence (AI) competencies for organizational performance: A B2B marketing capabilities perspective. *Journal of Business Research*. <https://osuva.uwasa.fi/bitstream/handle/>
- Nahar, K., Akhter, S., & Sharturaev, J. (2024). Impact of artificial intelligence on human resources management. MPRA Paper No. 120579. <https://mpra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/120579/>
- Nayem, Z., & Uddin, M. A. (2024). Unbiased employee performance evaluation using machine learning. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 10(2), Article 100243. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joitmc.2024.100243>
- Neyna, C. (2021). Employee productivity. <https://www.bnt/employee-productivity/20859>
- Oshogbunu, E. O., Amah, E., & Okocha, B. F. (2022). Management by objective and organizational productivity: A literature review. *South Asian Research Journal of Business and Management*, 4(3), 99–111. <https://doi.org/10.36346/sarjbm.2022.v04i03.003>
- Pap, J., Mako, C., Illessy, M., Kis, N., & Mosavi, A. (2022). Modeling organizational performance with machine learning. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 8(4), 177.
- Qureshi, T. M. (2017). Impact of employee participation on job satisfaction, employee commitment, and employee productivity. *International Review of Business Research*, 3, 54–68.
- Singh, J. (2024). 6 ways to unleash the power of AI in manufacturing. <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2024/01/how-we-can-unleash-the-power-of-ai-in-manufacturing/>
- Suleiman, I. G., Mustapha, L. O., & Agbi, S. E. (2023). Effect of cost control and cost reduction on profitability of manufacturing firms in Nigeria: A case of Nestle Nigeria Plc. *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, 4(5), 5234–5240.
- Thu, M. K., Beppu, S., Yarime, M., & Shibayama, S. (2022). Role of machine learning and organizational structure in science. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/358957743_role_of_machine_learning_and_organizational_structure_in_science
- Urvin, M. (2024). What are business operations managers and what do they do?

Zhang, X., Antwi-Afari, M. F., Zhang, Y., & Xing, X. (2024). The impact of artificial intelligence on organizational justice and project performance: A systematic literature and science mapping review. *Buildings*, 14(1), Article 259. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings14010259>